

Local Government in Australia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Carol Mills

Institute for Public Policy and Governance
University of Technology Sydney

Partners

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
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Canada

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The Country Report on Local Government in Australia is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

University of Technology Sydney: Carol Mills
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malferttheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Jamie Davies/Unsplash

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.2. Provision of Services in Regional and Rural Areas

Carol Mills, *Institute for Public Policy and Governance, University of Technology Sydney*

Relevance of the Practice

Australian local governments traditionally perform a range of regulatory functions including building certification, land use planning, development approvals, domestic pet management, parking, food and health inspections. While they continue to remain narrower than in many countries, there has been a progressive expansion of roles. This includes a growing range of economic, social and environmental services such as child care, youth programs, libraries, sport and recreation facilities, business development, environmental management and community health.

Rural and urban local governments in Australia provide very different kinds of services reflecting community needs and goals. The institutional frameworks which govern the local government system in Australia's states and the Northern Territory must accommodate very different kinds of organisation. A one size fits all approach can act as a constraint to councils in terms of their operation and the division of responsibilities between elected councillors, the organisation and the community, particularly in rural and regional areas.

Description of the Practice

In many rural areas, local governments provide services that would normally be offered by the market or by state government. For example, Brewarrina Shire Council has partnered with Charles Sturt University to provide free dental services to its residents; Gilgandra Shire Council in New South Wales (NSW) provides a range of community services such as homelessness services and aged care; and, the Town of Esperance in Western Australia (WA) provides a wide range of aged care services. Additionally, the provision of primary health care (General Practitioners, nurses etc.) in rural areas of Australia is often viewed as insufficient. In response to this, rural local governments have created alternative solutions. Some provide infrastructure for GPs to use, others run their own medical practices. For example, Sandstone Council in WA provides a nursing post and access to doctors via the Royal Flying Doctor service. The Western Australia Local Government Association (WALGA) recently carried out a survey of regional health services in the state. Based on the outcomes of this survey, WALGA recommended that a further engagement be carried out with local governments to clarify effective and self-generated solutions which other local governments have implemented to recruit and retain health professionals to their areas.

Assessment of the Practice

Little is known about the extent or innovation of the new approaches local governments are taking to meet the needs of their rural communities. More research is required to better understand this practice, and how rural councils can best be supported to secure the services their communities require.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

WALGA, 'Regional Health Services in Western Australia. Survey of Local Governments' (2018) <<https://walga.asn.au/getattachment/Policy-Advice-and-Advocacy/People-and-Place/Health-and-Wellbeing/WALGA-Regional-Health-Services-in-Western-Australia-Survey-of-Local-Governments-FINAL.pdf?lang=en-AU>>

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

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